

TRANSITIONING TO THE NEXT FRONTIER OF MEDICAL IMAGING AND THE BUSINESS CASE FOR AGILE LEADERSHIP PRACTICES

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Abstract

There have been significant changes in medical imaging since the discovery of x-rays by Wilhelm Roentgen in 1895. This paper examines recent developments in diverse imaging modalities including conventional radiography, ultrasound, mammography, computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), positron emission tomography (PET), and single photon emission tomography (SPECT). The paper also examines the adoption of disruptive technologies such as 3D printing, blockchain, cloud computing, augmented reality/virtual reality, and artificial intelligence and their impact on already existing imaging technologies, leading to profound modifications in medical imaging practice that were unimaginable few years ago. The paper assumes that leadership practices of the past may no longer fit the requirements of today's changing medical imaging landscape. The paper also delves into perspectives on agile leadership practices as organizations continue to make choices suitable for navigating these massive changes.

Keywords: Imaging Modalities; Disruptive Technologies; Agile Leadership

Introduction

Medical imaging has developed into a vital tool for providing healthcare in the modern day, and its uses are essential to many facets of patient care. It is helpful in research, teaching, interventional procedures, telemedicine, diagnosis and illness detection, treatment planning, and more. It also plays a critical role in patient engagement, which improves patient outcomes (Abdullah & Reed, 2018; Friebe & Illanes, 2023).

Absolutely, the field of medical imaging has witnessed remarkable advancements since the discovery of X-rays by the German physicist, Wilhelm Roentgen, in 1895. The advent and development of multiple imaging modalities have transformed medical practice to such an extent that, were it not for the immense capabilities of radiation therapy, ultrasound, mammography, positron emission tomography (PET), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computerized tomography (CT), conventional x-rays, and magnetic resonance imaging

(MRI), patient management would face a significant vacuum (Abdullah & Reed, 2018; Ilyas et al., 2023; Rubin, 2014; Weissleder & Nahrendorf, 2015; Theek et al., 2020).

While some evolving modalities like magnetic particle imaging (MPI) and optical imaging are at the nascent stages of their application in medicine (Taxt et al., 1998), the rise of algorithms in medical imaging has opened new vistas in healthcare delivery. The interactions between medical imaging and disruptive technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoTs), virtual reality and augmented reality (VR/AR), 3D printing, blockchain, and cloud computing have introduced new capabilities in workflow efficiency, diagnostic accuracy, personalized and targeted therapy, robotic-assisted interventions, and data storage and security (Manaf & Chhatlani, 2023; Harry, 2023; Ahmad et al., 2020; Abdullah & Reed, 2018; Pesapane et al., 2018; Alan et al., 2023; Vyas & Bhatt, 2017). Though it is widely debated by scholars, practitioners, and policy makers that the perils of the emerging technologies lie in unethical use and opacity (Cheatham et al., 2019), algorithm bias (Seyyed-Kalantari et al., 2021), safety and privacy risks (Alonso & Siracuse, 2023), and widening health inequalities (Hartlev, 2021; Fukuda-Parr & Gibbons, 2021; Currie & Hawk, 2021), there are several governance measures in place to confront the associated risks.

The field of medical imaging is fast-paced and dynamic, with constant technical advancements driving this dynamic. This necessitates responsive, adaptable, and forward-thinking leadership approaches. Can agile leadership practices offer the strategic fit in the context of flexibility, collaboration, change adaptability, and dynamism to help organizations effectively balance agility and stability as the next frontier of medical imaging unfolds with ongoing technological disruptions?

Highlights on Advances in Imaging Modalities

The first medical diagnosis was dependent solely on physical observation prior to the use of the mind and senses as diagnostic tools by Hippocrates (Berger, 1999). The discovery of X-rays by Wilhelm Roentgen in 1895 elevated medical diagnosis to a new height and sparked the development of numerous imaging technologies for clinical application (Panchbhai, 2015).

Certainly, medical imaging has undergone significant advancements over the past century, revolutionizing medical practice and contributing to improved patient outcomes. The journey of medical imaging has progressed from simple conventional radiography to highly sophisticated molecular imaging technologies (Ilyas et al., 2023; Mshnail et al., 2023; Taxt et al., 1998; Rego & Tan, 2006; Theek et al., 2020; Najjar, 2023). While there have been great advancements in conventional radiography, ultrasound, mammography, computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and molecular imaging over the years, hybrid imaging is a growing trend that combines functional and anatomical information

from various imaging modalities either through software or hardware fusion (Cherry, 2009; Busse, 2006; Hricak et al., 2010; Yadav & Yadav, 2020).

The objective of this section is to provide an overview of the principles, uses, and technical advancements related to different imaging techniques.

Conventional radiography, commonly known as X-ray imaging, remains one of the most widely used and accessible imaging modalities in medical practice. Its versatility allows for both diagnostic and interventional procedures. Film-based system has been used in conventional radiography for years before its substitution by computed radiography (CR), innovated by Fujifilm in 1983. The transition from film-based radiography to computed radiography (CR) marked a significant advancement in conventional radiographic imaging, offering several advantages and addressing various limitations associated with the traditional film-based systems (Sankaran, 2001). Another significant advancement in digital radiography is the development of solid-state image receptors, such as photosensitive flat panel arrays, micro-machined piezoelectric arrays, and quantum dots (Wolbarst & Hendee, 2006). These have resulted in better image quality, less radiation exposure and increased diagnostic accuracy. A fully digital picture archiving and transmission system, as well as cloud- or web-based image storage, are made possible by the shift to digital radiography (Seeram & Seeram, 2019). The search is still underway for x-ray detectors that can combine low-dose radiation, excellent resolution, large imaging areas, and flexibility, despite notable advancements in conventional radiography. (Ou et al., 2021).

Ultrasound (US) is another widely used imaging modality for clinical intervention and diagnosis and presents the health community with the merits of providing non-invasive, radiation-free, portable, real-time images, and cost-effective services (Jiang et al., 2023). In ultrasound imaging, multidimensional sonography has had a long history to become the technology in use today as new methods of data manipulation and software technology became widely available (Belohlavek et al., 1993; Fenster & Downey, 2000; Lees, 2001; Nelson & Pretorius, 1998; Huang & Zeng, 2017; Mozaffari & Lee, 2017). Ultrafast doppler ultrasound, elastography, and contrast-enhanced ultrasound (CEUS) have enjoyed widespread adoption in detecting diseases and abnormalities (Bercoff, 2011; Tanter & Fink, 2014; Gennisson et al., 2013; Furlow, 2009; Xu, 2009). High intensity focused ultrasound (HIFU) has application in a variety of therapies such as tissue ablation, image-guided drug delivery, sensitization to radiation therapy, and immune stimulation (Izadifar et al., 2020; Ter Haar & Coussios, 2007). Technological advances in miniaturization and wireless connectivity have led to smaller point-of-care ultrasound (POCUS) devices, no larger than a mobile telephone set, and often described as the new stethoscope with the potential to ease its use in awkward spaces or in low-resource settings (Frederiksen et al., 2012; Buerger & Clark, 2017). According to Strategic Market Research, the global point-of-care-ultrasound market was valued at USD3.24 billion in 2022 and is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 5.7% by 2030 to reach USD5.9billion.

While ultrasound technology has made significant strides in recent years, there are still concerns of limited reproducibility and operator dependence (Chan & Perlas, 2018; Diniz et al., 2020). However, robotic-assisted ultrasound imaging promises to overcome these shortcomings by reducing variability and ensuring consistent image acquisition (Jiang et al., 2023; Sarno et al., 2023). Robot-assisted ultrasound imaging systems could be categorized into three (3) approaches: autonomous ultrasound imaging, teleoperated ultrasound imaging, and human-robot cooperation (Monfaredi et al., 2015).

In **computed tomography (CT)**, extreme multidetector CT, including 256-, 320- and 640-row multidetector systems, have evolved (Lell et al., 2015; Ginat & Gupta, 2014; Samei & Pelc, 2020). One of the potential applications of high spatial resolution capabilities of extreme multidetector CT is quantitative volume imaging. The high temporal resolution and wide-area coverage offered by extreme multidetector CT represents a major shift from an imaging modality that provides solely anatomical data to one that can also provide functional information (Boone, 2006; Lowe & Kay, 2006; Cruz-Bastida et al., 2016). The mathematical models forming the basis of iterative reconstruction algorithms could not be implemented in CT until recently because the computational power necessary could be achieved only with high-performance computer processors (Hsieh et al., 2013; Geyer et al., 2015; Jiang & Wang, 2002). Several iterative reconstruction software packages are now commercially available for use in CT (Stiller, 2018). Remarkable improvements have also been recorded in spectral CT technology (Yeh et al., 2017; Schirra et al., 2014; Massat, 2018) as well as portable (mobile) CT (Sukrod et al., 2015; Peace et al., 2010; Wald et al., 2020). Photon-counting CT (PCCT) is another new technology with the potential to dramatically change clinical CT. Photon-counting CT can reduce radiation exposure, reconstruct images at a higher resolution, optimize the use of contrast agents, and create opportunities for quantitative imaging relative to current CT technology (Willeminck et al., 2018; Flohr et al., 2020; Hsieh et al., 2020; Taguchi et al., 2020).

In **mammography**, screen-film technology has been in use for over 40 years, and in the last 15 years has been replaced in most practices by full-field digital mammography, enabling viewing and manipulation of images on computer workstations (Kerlikowske et al., 2011; Skaane, 2009). One limitation of both screen film mammography and digital mammography is false positives and missed lesions caused by the superimposition of tissue in 2-D images (Souza et al., 2013; Faridah et al., 2008). Breast tomosynthesis technology is essentially a recent modification in mammography to enable the acquisition of a three-dimensional (3D) volume of thin section data, using reconstruction algorithms like those used in computed tomography (CT) (Kopans, 2014; Diekmann & Bick, 2011). Digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT) is therefore called quasi-3-D technology because it differentiates tissues in slices. Contrast enhanced-digital breast tomosynthesis is a combination of the projection techniques of breast tomosynthesis with intravenous contrast enhancement, thus providing both breast cancer morphology and vascular information (Diekmann & Bick, 2007; Lobbes et al., 2013).

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is known for its excellent soft tissue characterization, without the need for ionizing radiation (Theek et al., 2020). Since its introduction for clinical use in the 1980s, the modality has undergone several technical advances (Yousaf et al., 2018; Wilson et al., 2023). In 1993, research sites began to move from 1.5T to 3T systems to investigate the feasibility of higher field applications. This was followed in 1998 by the introduction of the first clinical 3T product (Blamire, 2008; Ai et al., 2012). Recently, ultra-high-field human MRI machines (4–14T) have been installed at several sites (Uğurbil, 2018; Trattinig et al., 2016; Moser et al., 2012). In addition to magnetic field strength, other hardware improvements have contributed greatly to improvements in MRI. Other critical developments include stronger imaging gradients, better receiver coil arrays, digital receiver technology, more powerful reconstruction computers, and improved patient comfort systems to minimize claustrophobia. Simultaneously, improved software-based image acquisition and reconstruction methods have led to newer MRI contrast mechanisms, faster image acquisition, and improved image quality. The recent advances have created newer and emerging MR methods such as MR spectroscopy, functional MRI (fMRI), quantitative MRI, diffusion and diffusion tensor imaging, perfusion MRI, MR elastography, to name but a few examples (Börnert & Norris, 2020).

Positron emission tomography (PET) is a noninvasive imaging modality that provides physiological information through the injection of radioactive compounds called radiotracers, detection of radiation, and measuring the distribution of the radiotracer. Recent advances in processing scintillator crystals, new algorithms for image reconstruction and data processing and new detector technologies have improved the design and performance of scanners built using these technologies. These advancements have enabled new applications in cardiology, oncology, neurology, and pediatrics due to the clinically useful information that it provides on tissue and organ function. In the early 1990s, the idea of a multimodal medical imaging system that could merge the anatomical information from CT and MRI with the functional information provided by PET was conceived (Jager et al., 2003). Clinical PET–CT imaging has demonstrated its value in diagnosing and staging many cancers. On the other hand, the advantage gained by combining PET and MR imaging is attributed to the superior capabilities of MR for soft tissue imaging relative to CT. PET–MR imaging can achieve truly simultaneous imaging due to its integrated design, unlike PET–CT (Pichler et al., 2008; Ramalho et al., 2014; Kogan et al., 2016; Vaquero & Kinahan, 2015).

Single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) is another rapidly changing field with new developments in both hardware technology and image-processing algorithms. Enhancements in scintillators and photon transducers as well as increased availability of semiconductor technology have occurred at the component level, permitting the development of more compact systems for use in a variety of applications (Madsen, 2017). New developments include the introduction of hybrid SPECT–CT systems to improve differentiation of physiological and pathological conditions (Schillaci, 2005; Bach-Gansmo

et al., 2010; Griffiths & Lee, 2006; Jacene et al., 2008). Intriguing new reconstruction algorithms have been developed with the potential to significantly reduce SPECT acquisition times without compromising diagnostic quality (Madsen, 2017).

Other emerging modalities of interest to the medical imaging community include magnetic particle imaging (MPI) (Buzug et al., 2012; Bakenecker et al., 2018; Tay et al., 2021), and optical imaging (Kenry & Liu, 2018; Dhawan et al., 2010). The clinical translation of MPI invented in 2005 is a huge challenge since it needs to compete with other clinically established imaging methods (Theek et al., 2020).

Advances in nanotechnology and materials science have paved the way for the development of a new generation of contrast agents in the field of medical imaging (Rosen et al., 2011; Wallyn et al., 2019; Han et al., 2019). However, the interactions between nanomaterials and biological systems are complex and not yet fully understood. Transitioning to consistent large-scale production poses another challenge. Continuous research, and adherence to regulatory guidelines are crucial for addressing these challenges (Hsu et al., 2023; Salinas et al., 2021).

Disrupting Medical Imaging

This section intends to review the evolving domain of the next generation of medical imaging in the lens of disruptive technologies. Păvăloaia & Necula (2023) argue that disruptive technologies are newer technologies that have the potential to exert an unexpected impact on already existing technologies. They are characterized as such by their revolutionary computational capability, seemingly infinite amounts of data generated, and unprecedented technological advancements (Jekov et al., 2022). These technologies by way of artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing, 3D printing, augmented reality/virtual reality (AR/VR), and blockchain are resulting in significant changes in the practice of medical imaging in ways unimaginable few years ago. These developments in emerging technologies are likely to impact imaging outcomes, leadership strategy, interdisciplinarity, risk management, and regulation and compliance in the wider healthcare 4.0 ecosystem.

3D Printing

3D printing has emerged as a transformative technology in the medical field, offering new possibilities for precision, and innovation. Its applications range from enhancing surgical planning and interventions to creating personalized medical solutions that cater to individual patient needs. As technology continues to advance, the impact of 3D printing on medicine is likely to expand even further.

In medical imaging, CT, MRI, multidimensional sonography and rotational angiography are capable of generating volumetric image data sets that could be used in producing high-quality 3D printing models (Rengier et al., 2010). As 3D printing is likely to progress rapidly, collaboration between radiographers and other healthcare professionals would be

essential in the emerging technology as a further step to improve patient care (Abdullah & Reed, 2018).

Despite the benefits of 3D printing, limitations to its widespread adoption lie in cost and size constraints of printed models (Elsayed et al., 2020).

Blockchain

With the advent of blockchain technology, it is now possible to use cryptographic methods to address many distributed system security challenges (Odeh et al., 2022). The creation of safe and secure systems for patient data or records is the primary use of blockchain in the healthcare industry, which sets it apart from other uses of the technology (Ghosh et al., 2023). In overcoming privacy and security-related issues in view of the volume and velocity of data that reside in imaging systems, blockchain technology offers significant prospects.

Augmented Reality (AR)/Virtual Reality (VR)

While both AR and VR technologies involve immersive experiences, the key difference lies in the level of immersion and the relationship with the real world. AR enhances the real world by adding virtual elements to it, allowing users to interact with both the physical and virtual components simultaneously. On the other hand, VR creates a fully immersive, computer-generated environment that replaces the real world entirely during the user's experience (Elsayed et al., 2020; Uppot et al., 2019).

As a result of large complex datasets in medical imaging, VR and AR are applied to visualize and understand the complex human anatomical relationships. The predecessors of this innovation include surface rendering (also known as shaded surface display), volume rendering, and Depth 3-dimensional (D3D) (Douglas et al., 2017).

In addition to image viewing and localization of abnormalities, successful use of this technology has been described in monitoring treatment response (Douglas et al., 2016), and image-guided interventional procedures (Elsayed et al., 2020).

VR and AR offer significant potential for patient counseling, education, and engagement in medical imaging. The technologies can be used to create immersive, 3-D virtual models for highlighting anatomical or pathological findings based on the patient's own imaging data (Uppot et al., 2019).

Cloud Computing

The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) describes cloud computing as a model for enabling convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction. It can take the form of software-as-a-service (SaaS)(allowing users to rent applications running on clouds instead of paying to

purchase these applications), platform-as-a-service (PaaS) (providing a development platform for users to design their specific applications), or infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) (where computer infrastructure including storage and network access is provided as a service) (Jadeja & Modi, 2012). The evolving landscape of cloud computing has provided compelling propositions to become the dominant repository for the management and display of medical images (Parikh & Mehta, 2015).

The demands of data storage, image processing, and sharing are what are primarily driving the adoption of cloud computing in medical imaging. The future of medical imaging is unavoidably interwoven with cloud computing technologies, given that the discipline has recently become entirely digital coupled with the inevitable requirement for storing vast volumes of data (Gerard et al., 2013). In its most basic form, cloud computing entails storing imaging data on remote servers and connecting them to the local hospital computers for rapid access, processing, and distribution (Kharat & Singhal, 2017). It has given rise to the concept called PACS cloud, which the fundamental idea is to do PACS outsourcing taking advantages of the clouds' elasticity and scalability, avoiding hardware obsolescence, providing universal access to imaging data anywhere and anytime (Silva et al., 2011). The main advantage of cloud computing is the option to pay for services as and when needed on demand, limiting the costly expense of software licenses and hardware (Patel, 2012).

A position paper, *Digital Transformation: Shaping the Future of Healthcare*, by Philips Healthcare illustrated the benefits of a cloud-based hub in creating a new form of tele-presence, where highly experienced radiographers could be stationed in a central imaging operations command centre to guide and assist less experienced colleagues across multiple remote locations in real-time while the patient is on the scanner table thereby reducing variability in diagnostic outcomes, and unforeseen disruptions.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Initially introduced into medical practice in 1976 when a computer algorithm was used in the diagnosis of an abdominal pain (Fogel & Kvedar, 2018), AI has made major inroads in medical imaging in the past decade (Jost et al., 2023; Najjar, 2023; Strohm et al., 2020). The first reports of AI's use in imaging dates to early 90s when it was utilized to detect microcalcifications in mammography (Driver et al., 2020). John McCarthy is credited to have first mentioned the term "Artificial Intelligence" in 1956 and implied the ability of computer systems to assume tasks that frequently can only be attained through human intelligence. In "Machines Who Think", McCorduck (2004) argues that AI has no defined endpoint but rather a dynamic frontier of emerging computer capabilities to push the boundaries of what machines can do. Russell et al. (2010) described the term, AI, as a set of computer systems with cognitive functions and human attributes to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence. Benbya et al. (2020) refer to AI as the "ability of machines to perform human-like cognitive tasks. AI could be deconstructed into a set of techniques of sub-disciplines including machine learning, deep learning, neural networks,

natural language processing, rule-based expert systems, robotic process automation, and robots (Benbya et al., 2020; Davenport, 2018). Due to the lack of consensus in definition, artificial intelligence is characterized more by its capabilities than by a specific definition (Collins et al., 2021). Berente et al. (2021) argue that in the presence of definitional ambiguity and absence of a singular agreed-upon definition for AI, “*AI is whatever we are doing next in computing*”. They conceive of AI as a process and “*the frontier of computational advancements that references human intelligence in addressing ever more complex decision-making problems.*”

Other definitions emphasize AI as a “set of techniques and sub-disciplines” (Gasser et al. 2017; Chartrand et al., 2017). The term, machine learning (ML) was coined by Arthur Samuel in 1959 to denote one of the techniques of AI (Samuel, 1959). Machine learning empowers systems to learn and improve from experience, enabling them to autonomously adapt and make decisions (Chattu, 2021). One of the most promising techniques of interest in medical imaging that falls under machine learning is deep learning. It uses sophisticated neural networks to detect patterns within input data to produce outputs. Deep learning can learn the relationships between pixels in a chest x-ray to detect pathologies (Liu et al., 2023).

According to Allied Market Research, the market size of AI in medical imaging was valued at USD1.9bn in 2022 and is projected to reach USD29.7bn by 2032, registering a CAGR of 32.1% from 2023 to 2032. The technology’s potential is driving a surge in investments from larger tech companies such as Google, Apple, IBM, and Microsoft (Alexander et al., 2020).

As the acceleration of AI in medical imaging is propelled by the rise in big data and advancements in computational power (Najjar, 2023), imaging AI solutions have been developed for image acquisition (Ranscaert et al., 2019; Panayides et al., 2020; Barragan-Montero et al., 2021), image reconstruction (Wang et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2021; Mandal et al., 2018), AI-assisted reporting (Lim et al., 2022; Bizzo et al., 2021; Grewal et al., 2023), multimodal image fusion (Li et al., 2021; James & Dasarathy, 2014), radiogenomics and precision medicine (Oikonomou et al., 2020; Lambin et al., 2017), and several other applications.

While the adoption of AI in medical imaging has been commended for its transformative benefits, several ethical challenges and risks pertaining to AI governance have been noted in practice (Currie & Hawk, 2021; Lekadir et al., 2023; Ahmed et al., 2023; Herington et al., 2023; Saw & Ng, 2022; Tripathi & Musiolik, 2023; Lewis et al., 2019).

The Business Case for Managing the Transition with Agility

Rapid innovations have created an extremely competitive, complex, dynamic, and a brave new world for organizations (Petermann & Zacher, 2021; Peters et al., 2022; Crnogaj et al., 2022). The digital revolution has also empowered modern-day patients as healthcare

consumers in ways that will re-invent new set of rules and models for service delivery to align their needs with the changing technological landscape (Pergolizzi Jnr et al., 2023).

Though organizations still adhere to the traditional management practices and principles as outlined by Peter Drucker, Henry Mintzberg, Henri Fayol, and other management scholars; however, the demands of the rapidly evolving modern environment can seriously undermine most of these principles. Dawson (1994) conceptualized the need for organizations to adopt change either in response to internal or external pressures or the need to respond to future competitive demands. The conventional methods of traditional change management are suitable for implementing these massive changes only in a restricted scale (Kupiek, 2021). Innovations have negligible effects if they are merely superimposed on existing organizational conditions. There are enormous benefits when investments in new technology also considers corresponding changes in organizational characteristics (Venkatraman, 1994).

Unfortunately, companies are not designed with speed in mind, and as a result, they frequently lack the flexibility to quickly react to changing circumstances. Conventional organizational designs are inherently anti-change due to their strong command and control structures, inflexible leadership hierarchies, resistance to new ideas and procedures, and inertia. (Hugos, 2009; de Jager, 2004; Scott & Davis, 2015).

Given the major impact that disruptive technologies have on medical imaging, how the field will evolve in the future will present innovative and change-ready organizations with opportunities to undercut well-established incumbents. A field of practice that changes at exponential speed, together with competition for talent on a global scale have led to the evolution of an agile organization, where the paradigm is that of an organization as a living organism as described by Chakaborty et al (2023). This could be related to Charles Darwin's theory of evolution and natural selection where the struggle for existence would allow only those with favourable traits to survive. The key is to embrace adaptability and acknowledge that what has historically worked may not meet the needs of the present and previous success stories cannot guarantee future performance or prosperity (Hizam-Hanafiah & Soomro, 2021). It is vital that the approach leverages agile best practices (Palfreyman & Morton, 2022). The new age requires new ways of operating, working across and beyond conventional boundaries, and the adoption of new routines, and high-performance work practices, such as self-managed teams, so that innovative thinking can be embedded in the organization (Holbeche, 2023).

Agility is a mindset, a way of thinking, and a collection of values that could ensure best and fastest adaptation to changes in the environment (Akkaya, 2020). According to Greineder & Leicht (2020), several theories and terms on agile leadership makes a uniform understanding of the concept difficult. However, they attempt to describe agile leadership to encompass those mindsets, leadership styles and practices, as well as the characteristics and competencies of leaders which are designed to support a rapid

response of an organization to changing environmental conditions and are therefore particularly suitable for the leadership of organizations with flat hierarchies.

The convergence of disruptive technologies and medical imaging and the situational management of unexpected changes in the context of VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity) has compelled many organizations to consider radical changes. The pressure from areas such as smart human resources (Fachrunnisa et al., 2020; Luthia, 2023), dynamic capabilities (Kaya, 2023), strategic flexibility (Kamasak et al., 2017; Nwachukwu & Vu, 2020; Lewis et al., 2014), resource allocation priorities (Kohnová et al., 2019), and managing business continuity and resilience more quickly and efficiently (Zawadski & Zywicki, 2016; Indiarti & Lantu, 2022) are becoming more evident in imaging practice today. Martin (2015) contends that the changes in the technological landscape have resulted in corresponding changes in the workforce in terms of job roles, diversity, and expectations in supporting cultural shifts, managing people and technology. Agility, therefore, promises strategic leadership that facilitates how organizations attract, develop, and retain the next-generation workforce. It will transform decision-making and the way teams are organized including how jobs are designed and performed. Agility is not a stand-alone capability. The beneficial values of agility such as adaptability, speed, innovation, and sustainability must be complemented by organizational resilience or the ability to retrospect and recover from significant setbacks (Holbeche, 2023; Tarigan et al., 2021).

Conclusion

Disruptive technologies will continue to inject anxieties into the field of medical imaging. The ongoing trend coexists with challenging choices for practitioners and decision-makers of how best to contain service reconfigurations, workforce transformation, innovation and technology management, and capital acquisition models that are fit for future.

Strategic agility has been mentioned in several published works as the critical capacity that organizations need to adapt successfully to disruptive change. Because agility is still a new concept in healthcare management, it requires learning and adaptation to fit the context of the organization.

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